

Integrating Structural Biology

Instruct-ULTRA

WP2 – Roadmap to the future of Instruct

Lead Beneficiaries: P8 – CSIC, P2- UOXF

Leader: P8 – CSIC

Deliverable D8.1 Prototype process for data transfer defined in subtask 8.1.1

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Project objective

To increase the quality and integration of the data being acquired at all installations, including home laboratories, promoting the incorporation of the appropriate metadata and exploring ways to provide archive of raw original data produced at all Instruct Centres with appropriate DOIs.

Executive summary

We report on the tests undertaken to establish the technical requirements of a data archive/retrieval system to preserve and share scientific data across Instruct-ERIC facilities. Network monitoring tests were undertaken to assess the data transfer capabilities of various research facilities, highlighting the importance of network topology on transfer reliability, especially at the local level. The process used to archive and retrieve large data sets has evolved from a prototype process to a proven solution that could be adopted to centralise and share data between Instruct-ERIC Centres.

1. Introduction

Work Package 8 of the Instruct-ULTRA programme focuses on increasing the quality and integration of the data that is being acquired across Instruct-ERIC Centres, promoting the incorporation of appropriate metadata, and exploring ways to provide a permanent archive of the original, raw data.

Task 8.1 focusses on raw (and processed) data, and developing metadata services that fulfil Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) principles.

The aim of this report (sub task 8.1.1) is to establish the technical requirements and develop a prototype at the Diamond Light Source (DLS) for data transfer and retrieval, information capture of raw data, and to access resources to produce derived data. The intention is that the prototype could easily be adopted by other synchrotrons, or used as a central Instruct-ERIC archive. The report also highlights how a similar service for archive and retrieval could be provided to other Instruct-ERIC Centres.

The work has been carried out by Diamond Light Source, UK (third party to P2 – UOXF) and Centro Nacional de Biotecnología, Centro Superior de Investigaciones Científicas Spain (P8 – CSIC).

2. Current landscape

The Instruct-ULTRA project was established to promote scientific research services across the life sciences. It also provides a community to share best practice and foster collaboration between research centres. Its membership includes large national facilities (including synchrotrons, such as Diamond) as well as academic and industrial centres.

Some key characteristics and trends across the life sciences research landscape have been identified:

- Modern structural biology techniques generate large volumes of data (10s of TB).
- Research centres vary in the number of instruments and support staff (i.e. synchrotrons *versus* home labs).
- Smaller facilities are faced with the choice of using cloud services to archive data (an expensive option for large volumes of scientific data), hosting their own centres (associated with high up-front costs and a large number of support staff), or potentially using national / European institutions.

Diamond, and other facilities such as the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF), use ICAT (Information CATalogue)¹ and associated tools as a method for storage and archiving. In recent years, toolsets to integrate storage and archiving have evolved from prototype processes to full production for use across research facilities.

ICAT and the associated storage approach have benefited from lessons learned through large international scientific programs such as CERN. The challenge is how to make these processes available to a wider range of centres across the Instruct-ERIC community.

It is also worth noting that a number of synchrotrons across Europe also use information management systems to store metadata about experiments. For example, the Information Management System for Protein Crystallography (ISPyB)² is used at the Diamond (UK), ESRF (France), and MaxIV (Sweden) synchrotrons. ISPyB has also been the focus of intense work within Instruct-ERIC, so as to interface the management system with the image processing software developed at CNB-CSIC (XMIPP (X-Window-based Microscopy Image Processing Package)³ and Scipion⁴ (a Cryo-electron microscopy image processing framework)). A growing number of Cryo-EM facilities worldwide are using Scipion, hence interfacing with iSPyB unlocks broad capabilities for Information Management. ISPyB provides metadata across the lifecycle of experiments (such as crystallography, Cryo-EM and other techniques) including shipping, sample information, data collection, processing, and links to publishing structures through the Protein Data Bank (PDB). As such, it can provide a rich source of information for researchers in the life sciences. However, ICAT and ISPyB are currently separate systems and the data stored in ISPyB is only available to the original research team.

3. Future Landscape

In the next few years, more scientific facilities will be adopting an open data policy for publically funded research. As such, an increasing amount of information will need to be made available to researchers across the life sciences. Instruct-ERIC is well placed to provide common services to the life science community, by leveraging and sharing best practice across its Members.

Conceivably, a common data archive with suitable search and retrieval services could be provided through programmes developed by Instruct-ERIC. These programmes would allow smaller institutions to take advantage of modern scientific techniques and instruments, without building large data centres of their own. A common data archive

would also provide a common service for the broader life science community to access earlier research and results.

The ability to search and identify experiments of interest will only be practical if sufficiently rich metadata is stored alongside the raw and processed data. Therefore, the rich metadata available in systems such as ISPyB could be exploited to enhance the data archive. The plan for providing suitable metadata is the subject of a subsequent report (D8.2). This report will focus on describing a process for data archiving and retrieval as an example of future services.

4. Description of work

The project work can be divided into the processes for data transfer, archiving, retrieval and testing.

4.1 The data transfer process

The scale of the challenge cannot be understated. Modern structural biology techniques generate large volumes of raw and processed data, especially as diffraction experiments and Cryo-EM measurements push the boundaries of hardware detectors and streaming data processing. Whilst few Instruct-ERIC Centres manage the volume of instruments of a national synchrotron facility, the lessons learned from dealing with data management at large facilities can be applied to other Centres.

The long-term archive and retrieval service for Diamond is provided under a Service Level Agreement (SLA) by the UK Science Technology and Facilities Council (STFC). The STFC developed the archive as part of their role in the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) collaboration; hence, the long term archive at STFC is based on the CERN Advanced Storage (CASTOR) system. The STFC provide archiving services for both CERN and the LHC experiments, as well as UK national facilities such as the Central Laser Facility, the ISIS Neutron and Muon Source, and the Diamond Light Source.

The Diamond Light Source has been operational since 2007 and, since this time, has amassed 20 PB of raw and processed data, supporting a range of scientific institutions. However, only approximately 6 % of the volume of the DLS archive has been accessed. Commercial cloud vendors (Amazon, Google, Microsoft, etc.) can provide long term storage solutions, and the cost for such “cold” storage services is similar between

vendors: approximately \$ 0.004 (0.0035 euros) per GB per month, as of 2019. Even at the current for cold storage rates, the size of Diamond’s archive would equate to \$ 960K year (or € 843K per year).

4.2 The archive process

The process for archiving at the Diamond Light Source is based on a two-stage approach. Beamline instruments at the DLS require the use of high-performance detectors, with large data rates that require access to a high-performance file system, such as the IBM General Parallel File System (GPFS), which are optimised for fast read and write speeds. However, building a long-term storage solution from such high-performance file systems can be expensive; hence, the process at Diamond is to move data to a long-term tape archive after a specified period (i.e. 40 days).

The process of archiving data relies on a number of software applications and technologies. The general steps are as follows:

- the data acquisition software writes raw data to the disk;
- the acquisition software or processing pipeline software writes an XML file (a “drop file”) describing the data collected;
- the XML file is processed by an intermediate server where validation checks are made;
- if validated, the server informs the long-term storage service of the new data with basic metadata;
- Logging for operational monitoring and metrics is performed.

Fig 1 shows a high-level view of the data archiving process at the Diamond Light Source. The first part of the process is within the Diamond network, with the Data Archive tool (the DARC server) determining if the drop file is valid and therefore ready to archive. The second part of the process (starting from the “ready to archive” point) runs two processes in parallel: the first path deals with archiving the data files, whilst the second updates the ICAT metadata storage. The metadata contains basic information about the experimental session and datasets.

Within Diamond, there are many different research groups with different requirements and software analysis implementations. Therefore, the specific software applications involved in archiving varies between groups (from simple scripts to applications using messaging frameworks).

Figure 1 – The high-level archive process at the Diamond Light Source.

Figure 2, which shows the archiving process at Diamond in more detail, is representative of the system that would be implemented by Instruct-ERIC Centres adopting a similar approach.

Figure 2 – The technical archive process at the Diamond Light Source.

The blocks on the left hand side of the diagram show the different tools that generate the XML “drop files”. The Macromolecular Crystallography (MX) group at the DLS has an established data processing pipeline that leverages an ActiveMQ messaging service for communication. In this case, a message containing the XML data is published for consumption directly by the DARC server.

For other beamlines, the Generic Data Acquisition (GDA) software can write drop files directly to a specified file path. For electron microscopy (EM) instruments, the data collection software runs on Windows machines and so there is a staged process to move data from local (to the instrument) storage to the GPFS file system. Once stored in the GPFS file system, transfer scripts create the drop files for consumption by the DARC server.

Further scripts run by the Scientific Computing group at the DLS deal with edge cases, such as in the case of transfer errors. Archiving scripts are run during a session rather than waiting until a session is closed in order to smooth access and transfer rates and prevent spikes in file system access.

The DARC server itself consists of multiple services that communicate via its own ActiveMQ service. XML messages are read either from the MX ActiveMQ listener, or via

an Apache Camel File component for monitoring the data file on disk. In all cases the XML file is validated for schema and content based on a local ruleset (i.e. files outside of the core data file system, such as temporary files and folders, should not be archived).

Validated requests result in the DARC server writing to STFC provided components that interface to the archive service. The ICAT ingestor writes data to the ICAT database with simple metadata, while the XML listener requests data transfer to the storage client. Invalid requests are not discarded but logged into a separate drop zone for manual processing.

The StorageD service takes input files and aggregates the files into chunks suitable for efficient archiving. A complementary service de-aggregates the files when retrieving specific data files from the aggregated data store.

The retrieval services available from STFC include TopCAT, a mountable virtual file system for browsing data (Filesystem in Userspace, FUSE), and a Globus endpoint (Figure 3).

Figure 3 - System overview of the STFC-managed archive.

4.3 The retrieval processes

Data from a visit is retained on Diamond's high-performance file system for 40 days after the end of a session, following which the data is only accessible from the data archive. There are different options for users to retrieve their data, depending on whether the data is still on "spinning disks" or has been archived on tape.

The methods for Diamond users to retrieve their data include:

- Data Dispenser;
- SynchWeb/ISPyB;
- Diamond (or STFC) Globus endpoint;
- TopCAT.

The next sub-sections describe each of the data retrieval approaches. If the required data size is small and the 40 day time period has not expired, ftp and rsync options are also available. However, as these are standard copying tools, they will not be discussed here. For large data sets (i.e. > 20GB), standard ftp clients are not resilient enough to provide reliable transfers.

a) Local Storage: Data Dispenser

While a user is on site, it is possible to transfer raw and processed data on to portable hard disk drives (using USB or eSATA connections) at the beamline. Historically, this allowed users to collect their data at the end of a visit, however the increasing size of data sets means this is often impractical. Moreover, an increasing number of visits are remote sessions, for which online methods to archive and retrieve data are preferable.

b) Access via the SynchWeb/ISPyB Web application

At Diamond, the web application for ISPyB is called SynchWeb.⁵ SynchWeb provides users with access to the rich metadata stored within the ISPyB database for each experiment. Largely developed for the MX community, SynchWeb is developing features that also support other life science (e.g. Cryo-EM) and physical science techniques. The results of auto-processing tools (results, graphs, logs, etc.) are made available through the SynchWeb interface, which is used primarily at the MX beamlines at Diamond. Processed data include MTZ reflection files that are typically in the region of 10s to 100s of MB, otherwise larger files are not recommended for download via SynchWeb. Direct download of raw data is not supported.

c) Globus

For raw data or large processed files, Diamond provides a Globus⁶ endpoint with tools and services for reliable file transfer and for sharing data between institutions. Various software subscriptions are available for academic and commercial organisations. The underlying transport solution is based on GridFTP.

Within 40 days of the experimental session ending, users can retrieve their data directly from the Globus file system, after which time the data will be made available through TopCAT and the data archive. Data from the Diamond Globus endpoint can be transferred to a local PC or another Globus endpoint if the user's institution has one setup.

Personal desktop software is available to allow a user's machine to connect to other Globus endpoints. However, a critical factor for the rate of data transfer is the network optimisation and topology between the user's machine and the facility (e.g. the network link between the user's PC/institution's endpoint and Diamond).

The impact of network latency on throughput is described briefly in Section 4.

d) TopCAT

For historical sessions, the TopCAT web-based user interface is the main route for users to access their data. TopCAT allows users to browse through a list of investigations (experiment sessions), and the datasets of interest can be added to a cart (similar to an online shopping site). A number of options are then available for downloading the data:

- HTTPS: downloads data set as a zip file through the web browser. Only suitable for small data files.
- Globus: restages the datasets to an STFC managed Globus endpoint.
- Diamond file system: an option that is currently in development. In future, this option will restore the data to its original location on the Diamond high-performance file system.

Name	Datafile Count	Create Time	Modified Time
analysed	8 files	2014-04-10 21:36:10	2014-04-10 21:36:10
Kamin-K3_1_dnafiles	1 file	2008-07-24 13:45:54	2010-02-17 18:00:41
Kamin-K3_1_dnafiles-3	1 file	2008-07-24 11:36:01	2010-02-17 18:00:40
trypsin_1_dnafiles-36	1 file	2008-07-23 08:51:50	2010-02-17 18:00:40
trypsin_1_dnafiles-35	1 file	2008-07-22 13:20:34	2010-02-17 18:00:38
Kamin-K1_1_dnafiles	1 file	2008-07-21 11:41:08	2010-02-17 18:00:40
Kamin-K1_1_dnafiles-1	1 file	2008-07-21 11:21:06	2010-02-17 18:00:36
trypsin_1_dnafiles-34	1 file	2008-07-21 11:20:01	2010-02-17 18:00:38
Kamin-K3_1_dnafiles-2	1 file	2008-07-17 11:58:46	2010-02-17 18:00:36
Kamin-K3_1_dnafiles-1	1 file	2008-07-16 16:31:58	2010-02-17 18:00:36
trypsin_1_dnafiles-27	1 file	2008-04-23 12:33:46	2010-02-17 18:00:38
trypsin_10_dnafiles	1 file	2008-04-22 12:20:59	2010-02-17 18:00:41
trypsin_1_dnafiles-26	1 file	2008-04-22 12:20:59	2010-02-17 18:00:38

Figure 4 – The TopCAT interface at the Diamond Light Source.

One of the biggest challenges with TopCAT and its underlying data model is generic. Experience from Diamond has illustrated that adding rich metadata for structural biology experiments does not work well. In contrast, the ISPyB database contains a much richer set of metadata, which would help researchers to retrieve results of interest. Currently, data policies restrict metadata access to Diamond users only but in future, government-funded research will be made open access after an embargo period of three years, bringing Diamond in line with other synchrotrons, such as the ESRF. The challenge is in how to allow users searching for useful research data to query across ICAT and ISPyB; ideally across all Instruct-ERIC institutions. Future tasks in the programme will address this issue.

4.4 Testing Data Transfer Process

The Globus transfer service and the underlying GridFTP technology are designed to transfer data between two distributed sites, and the architecture is designed to be resilient to lost packets by using parallel FTP (File Transfer Protocol) streams. However, to ensure data integrity, lost packets need to be monitored and re-transmitted, leading

to additional network traffic. Therefore, the rate of data transfer is determined by the weakest link in the network.

Diamond follows the Science Demilitarised Zone (DMZ)⁷ design pattern for data access. The Science DMZ was proposed and developed by the Energy Sciences Network⁸ to address the challenges of high-volume data transfer, remote experiment control, and data visualisation. A Science DMZ has four components:

- A network infrastructure designed for high performance applications and to minimise packet loss, located at the edge of the campus/facility.
- Dedicated Data Transfer Nodes (DTNs), including optimised hardware, tuned operating system settings, and software tools such as Globus toolkit.
- Performance monitoring and diagnostics tools to regularly assess transfer speeds and identify issues (e.g. perfSONAR).
- Security policies designed for high-performance data transfer environments (use of access control lists, tailored firewall rules, etc.).

Figure 5 – The Science DMZ high-level network architecture.

Before the Science DMZ pattern was adopted at Diamond, transfers to local research centres were typically ~50Mbps. Following the configuration of the Science DMZ, transfers between Diamond and local centres is ~1Gbps. The connection to an ESNet test point in New York show rates up to 2Gbps.

The Data Transfer Node and monitoring node are hosted as close to the perimeter of the site (or campus) as practical because enterprise firewalls are designed with security rules to cope with many different types of network traffic.

The final stage is to monitor the network. Placing high performance transfer nodes behind general purpose firewalls provides a bottleneck on fast transfers. To illustrate this point, a set of simple tests were conducted between Diamond and the CSIC Centre in Madrid. Diamond is part of the perfSONAR network:⁹ a set of tools for monitoring network bandwidth (throughput) and latency between sites. Regular tests can be scheduled using perfSONAR to monitor the connections between nodes on a network. Figure 5, a dashboard with a snapshot of results from the Diamond node, shows that the connection speed between Diamond and the Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron (DESY) is over 3Gbps. At Diamond, the network interface between the data transfer node and the wide area network is 10Gbps (illustrated by the internal LAN test in Figure 6).

SOURCE	DESTINATION	THROUGHPUT	LATENCY (MS)	LOSS
perfsonar.diamond.ac.uk 193.62.221.6 Details Traceroute	192.100.78.45	→ 9.84 Gbps ← 9.57 Gbps	→ 0.255 (rtt) ← n/a	→ n/a ← n/a
perfsonar.diamond.ac.uk 193.62.221.6 Details Traceroute	perfsonar-ps-04.desy.de 131.169.7.30	→ 3.76 Gbps ← 3.87 Gbps	→ n/a ← n/a	→ n/a ← n/a
perfsonar.diamond.ac.uk 193.62.221.6 Details Traceroute	perfsonar06i.dl.ac.uk 148.79.1.168	→ 124 Mbps ← n/a	→ 4.55 ← n/a	→ 0.013% ← 100.000%
perfsonar.diamond.ac.uk 193.62.221.6 Details	perfsonar06i.dl.ac.uk 148.79.1.156	→ 98.7 Mbps ← n/a	→ 4.59 ← n/a	→ 0 ← 100.000%

Figure 6 – A dashboard showing perfSONAR results from the Diamond Science DMZ.

To illustrate the impact of packet loss, a number of tests were carried out between Diamond (acting as a centralised Instruct-ERIC Centre) and CSIC Madrid (acting as a client research centre). While CSIC does not formally follow the Science DMZ pattern, it does have a Data Transfer Node (DTN) close to the perimeter of the campus network. In addition, a perfSONAR node was installed on the same network switch as the DTN. As testing progressed between the Diamond and CSIC sites, the latter adopted more of the Science DMZ principles (i.e. network monitoring and optimised hardware/software settings) and achieved higher transfer rates.

The results network monitoring delineate three types of research facility, based on their data transfer capabilities:

1. A single laboratory with no resources or assistance with data handling (exemplified in the extreme case of using a home broadband connection).
2. An Instruct Centre where a reduced team of IT and data experts are working with experimental groups.
3. An Instruct Centre supported by expertise from a wider Instruct service.

It is clear from the results of the networking monitoring tests (summarised below) that the assistance, experience and developments of a large facility (acting as a 'prototype') can support the reduced complement of data experts at a typical Instruct-ERIC Centre, making the difference between a fully workable system and one that simply cannot cope with the high demands of structural biology.

5. Results

5.1 Home network to Synchrotron (single laboratory)

Network Route: Farnborough, UK to Diamond, UK

Network Card: 1Gbps via network router to Cable modem (200Mbps)

Command: pscheduler task throughput --dest 193.62.221.6 --duration 30

Results:

Interval (s)	Throughput	Retransmits
0.0 - 30.0	13.34Mbps	597

As expected, the transfer from an un-optimised home office location does not achieve high transfer rates.

5.2 Instruct-ERIC Centre to Synchrotron

Network Route: CSIC, Spain to Diamond, UK

Network Card: 1 Gbps and 10 Gbps cards on a Data Transfer Node (DTN) within Science DMZ

Command: pscheduler task throughput --dest 193.62.221.6 --duration 30

Results:

Network Card Configuration	Interval (s)	Throughput	Retransmits
1 Gbps	0.0 - 30.0	641.75 Mbps	0
10 Gbps (unoptimised)	0.0 - 30.0	724.42 Mbps	1
10 Gbps (optimised)	0.0 - 30.0	1.26 Gbps	4605
10 Gbps (capped)	0.0 - 30.0	1.29 Gbps	4173

Initially the DTN at CNB-CSIC had a 1 Gbps network card. Upgrading to a 10 Gbps card did not immediately improve transfer rates (un-optimised). At 10 Gbps the operating system network buffers needed to be changed to optimise the flow of network packets (optimised) and recommendations from ESN⁸ were used. Finally, capping the throughput test at 1.29 Gbps established a smoother (and higher) result. The dropped packets for the capped test occurred when establishing the initial connection.

5.3 Summary of Results

Combining the results into a single chart illustrates the impact of network topology on transfer rates (Figure 7). The results show that the network connection from the CSIC in Madrid (approximately 1000 miles) is significantly better than a connection from within the UK (approximately 45 miles) via home broadband connection. Thus, the same centralised endpoint can experience significantly slower transfer rates purely due to the

network topology between centre and client. The high number of re-transmits for the optimised 10 Gbps case reflect the throughput test attempting to maximise the network traffic and hitting limits above 1.3 Gbps. A steady transfer rate of ~1.29 Gbps can be achieved with a 10 Gbps card at CNB-CSIC. At this point the bottlenecks appear to be outside the campus firewall and more investigation would be needed to achieve higher throughput rates.

Figure 7 – The throughput rates between Diamond (UK) and a home office (UK) at 1 Gbps via network router to Cable modem, and between Diamond and CNB-CSIC in Spain for 1 and 10 Gbps network card configurations. The results show that any centralised archive/transfer service will only be as useful as the networking between the sites. The closer the data transfer endpoint to the WAN link the better the throughput but network cards of 10 Gbps need optimised network configurations.

5.4 Globus Transfer

Finally, tests were run to transfer data between Diamond (UK) and CNB-CSIC (Spain) using Globus. A test session was used with initial transfers of 1-10 GB to establish a baseline transfer rate (

Figure 8). The Globus service allows users to initiate transfers between any two endpoints, subject to the user having appropriate authentication credentials and permissions at each site.

Figure 8 – The Globus transfer between CNB-CSIC, Spain and Diamond, UK.

The transfer rates recorded with the 10 G network card at CNB-CSIC were initially 76 MB/s (~600 Mbps) but optimising the TCP network buffers on the DTN at CNB achieved a maximum effective speed of 168 MB/s (equivalent to ~1.3 Gbps). Sustaining the optimised data transfer rates, a 1 TB data file would take approximately 1 hour and 40 minutes to transfer. Note that 1 TB of data represents several hours of data collection, even at the fastest microscopes for data acquisition (in 2019). Although real-world performance is expected to vary due to the number of simultaneous users and connections, at these rates the use of a remote facility for archiving and retrieval is feasible

6. Conclusions and Recommendations

- The process used to archive and retrieve large data sets has evolved from a prototype process to a proven solution that could be adopted to centralise and share data between Instruct-ERIC Centres.
- The ICAT service with supporting tools (such as DARC Server) provides data storage and retrieval solution for large facilities (DLS, ESRF etc.) and potentially Instruct-ERIC Centres.
- Large-scale facilities (e.g. synchrotrons) could provide Instruct-ERIC with a technical solution for integrated services for data transfer and retrieval, leveraging the investment in national centres (subject to suitable funding and commercial agreements).
- Any Instruct-ERIC-wide solution needs to recognise the importance of network topology on transfer reliability, especially at the local level.
- Adopting the Science DMZ design pattern will allow Instruct-ERIC facilities to take advantage of fast transfer rates for remote archiving and retrieval services.

7. References

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